

Metal Complexes of 1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-Phenanthrol (PAP) as Visual Indicators in Acid-Base Titrations

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Zinc(II), cadmium(II) and manganese(II) complexes of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-phenanthrol (PAP) have been recommended as visual indicators for extractive end points in acid-base titrations. pH intervals of colour change and $pH_{\frac{1}{2}}$ have been determined.

THE use of metal complexes as visual indicators in acid base titrations has been investigated in recent years¹⁻⁴. The present communication describes the use of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and manganese(II) complexes of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-phenanthrol (PAP) as extraction indicators in the titrations of a strong base against a strong acid. PAP is a newly synthesized ligand⁵ of promising analytical potentiality⁶⁻⁹.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Spectrophotometer —Uvicam SP 600
pH meter —Metrohm, E 350
Titration flasks —100 ml quick fit pyrex conical flask.

Reagents :

PAP was prepared by the method of Chiswell *et al.*⁵ For preparing the complexes an ethanolic solution of PAP was added to aqueous solution of metal ion concerned in 1 : 2, metal : ligand ratio (sodium hydroxide solution was also added in the case of manganese(II) complex). Intense pink colour developed instantaneously. The contents were refluxed on a water bath for about 2 hrs. On concentration, the complexes precipitated out. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed thoroughly with water and benzene and dried at 80° in an electric oven. The results of elemental analysis of the complexes show the formation of a $M(PAP)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ complex in each case.

The indicator solutions were prepared by dissolving 0.020 g of complexes in 100 ml chloroform. Freshly prepared 0.1M NaOH and 0.1M HCl (both BDH, AR) were used for titrations.

Absorption spectra

Absorption spectra of the complexes were recorded in chloroform at different pH values (3-10, using CH_3COONa/HCl , CH_3COOH/CH_3COONa and $CH_3COONa/NaOH$ buffers). Chloroform solutions (10 ml, 0.002M) of the complexes were taken in a

Fig. 1. Visible absorption spectra of PAP-Zn(II) complex in chloroform at different pH of aqueous phase. (●) pH 8.6; (▲) pH 5.8; (□) pH 3.8.

TABLE I

Complex	pH of isolation	Colour	m.p.	%M calcd. (found)	%C calcd. (found)	%N calcd. (found)	%H calcd. (found)
$Zn(C_{19}H_{12}N_3O)_2$	7.3	pink	> 300°	8.16 (8.19)	68.96 (68.52)	12.71 (12.54)	3.63 (3.53)
$Cd(C_{19}H_{12}N_3O)_2$	7.2	pink	> 300°	16.60 (15.80)	64.39 (63.80)	11.86 (11.45)	3.39 (3.32)
$Mn(C_{19}H_{12}N_3O)_2$	9.0	pink	> 300°	8.43 (8.30)	70.06 (69.62)	12.91 (12.91)	3.68 (3.96)

series of 50 ml quickfit glass stoppered bottles, 10 ml of buffer was added and the mixture was shaken thoroughly. After the aqueous and chloroform layers separated, the organic layer was taken out and centrifuged to remove water droplets. Visible spectra of clean chloroform solutions were then recorded. Results are presented in Figs. 1-3.

Fig. 2. Visible absorption spectra of PAP-Cd(II) complex in chloroform at different pH of aqueous phase. (●) pH 8.5; (▲) pH 6.6; (□) pH 5.8.

Fig. 3. Visible absorption spectra of PAP-Mn(II) complex in chloroform at different pH of aqueous phase (●) pH 9.3; (▲) pH 6.3; (□) pH 4.5.

Methods of titration

10.0 ml of 0.1M sodium hydroxide solution was pipetted into a titration flask and 3 ml of the indicator solution was added, titration was then performed with 0.1M hydrochloric acid solution. Near the end point, the flask was stoppered and shaken after each addition of titrant. Colour change in the organic layer from pink to yellow showed the end point.

Results and Discussion

Titration Precision

Eight titrations were performed with each indicator and the ability of the indicators to change colour

sharply was tested. The precision obtained for each set is given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PRECISION OF TITRATION

Indicator	maximum deviation from the mean		Average deviation from the mean	
	(ml)	(%)	(ml)	(%)
Zn(II)-PAP complex	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Cd(II)-PAP complex	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Mn(II)-PAP complex	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05

Effect of varying indicator concentration

Changing the volume of the indicator solution from 2 ml to 5 ml in all the cases does not affect the titration results, so that 3 ml of the indicator solution (0.02%) is recommended for the titrations. Less than 2 ml of the indicator produced false end points due to indistinguishability of colour change. More than 5 ml of the indicator solution causes the deviation from the mean results to the extent of +0.1 ml.

pH intervals of colour change and pH_1^*

The pH dependence of the absorbance of the organic phase at λ_{max} (470 nm) is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. pH dependence of optical density at 470nm.

I Zn(II)-PAP complex
II Cd(II)-PAP complex
III Mn(II)-PAP complex.

The extreme pH values of the colour change intervals were chosen to correspond to 1/11 and 10/11 of the total colour development in the organic phase as read from the absorbance versus pH curves. pH_1^* , the pH value corresponding to one-half colour development of organic phase, can be taken as approximate pH at which the extraction indicator signals titration end point. Values of pH_1^* as evaluated from the absorbance versus pH graphs has been given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—ESTIMATED pH INTERVALS OF COLOUR CHANGE

Indicator	pH interval of colour change	pH _i *
Zinc-complex	5.80—7.00	6.40
Cadmium-complex	6.15—8.35	7.50
Manganese-complex	5.25—6.80	6.02

Visible absorbance spectra

The visible absorbance spectra of the complexes at various pH values are given in Figs. 1-3. It may be noted that the complexes in acidic medium give the same spectra as that of the PAP⁶⁻⁸. It is evident, therefore, that the complexes are stable only in neutral and alkaline media and in acidic solution dissociate as follows :

where M stands for Zn(II), Cd(II) and Mn(II) and LH for the PAP molecule.

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